

Doing More with Less – Measuring Efficiency in the Primary Care Management of Chronic Diseases, Maternal and Child Care

Authors: Joana Pestana and Pedro Pita Barros

ABSTRACT

Purpose: This paper examines the variations in efficiency between three organizational models of primary health care in Portugal using an extensive set of indicators related to the quality of care of specific groups - patients with chronic diseases, mothers and children. Our special interest was to establish the extent to which mixed payment mechanisms with financial incentives and the autonomy of the teams to define the inputs, generate variations in efficiency. Stimulus to efficiency improvements were attempted in several countries by means of organizational innovations and incentives. Amid these efforts was the reform introduced in Portugal in 2005. During the financial downturn the virtues of the new organizational models - administrative local clusters and Family Health Units (FHU) with more autonomous multidisciplinary teams and performance related payments - were praised in the adjustment program. After 2014, however, the creation of these units has stalled, and concerns about the financing of such schemes have been raised. The health units are the main providers of primary health care services within their catchment area and are mainly tax financed. The FHU cover approximately 50% of the population and have two sequential phases, with different incentive schemes. The FHU teams have greater flexibility in managing their practices, i.e. can define the efficient dimension of the units, services provided, opening hours and the substitution between productive factors. The health ministry limits the opening of the new practices creating pressure to improve performance and cost containment. Nevertheless, despite presenting better outcomes with greater patient lists, we observe very low heterogeneity in the dimension and skill mix of FHU. The ratio of nurses to physicians is low (on average 1.1 per unit) and even lower in the FHU. The diversity in clinical expertise is also low and the proportion of physicians above 55 years is the highest in Europe. These workforce characteristics and the limitations of the incentives schemes can impair improvements in patient care and lead to potential cost inefficiency.

Methodology: In this study 790 primary care units are analyzed. Using data from the National Health performance indicators from 2015 to 2018, we look at the relationships between the units' context, structure, remuneration methods and their outcomes. We apply parametric production and cost frontier efficiency measurement to identify the most efficient units, which are set as a reference to recognize inefficiencies. We also use multivariate multilevel analysis to account for the combination of multiple objectives and the hierarchical nature of the system. Outputs in the first frontier are measured using 30 quality indicators of process and intermediary outcomes pooled into 5 indexes. The second frontier is based on costs, including human resources costs and prescription. We use different input scenarios combining the labor inputs and quality, and control for the underlying patient case-mix and socioeconomic conditions.

Contributions: Overall, we find that teams outside FHU present relative lower efficiency scores. The size of the team does not conduce to less inefficiencies. As expected, the FHU efficiency scores are less influenced by the administrative local cluster's performance.